

e-ISSN: 3107-3875

**Volume 09 Issue 01
Jan - Jun 2026**

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Submission Date : Jan 20, 2026

Copyright Received Date: Jan 22, 2026

Transformation of Interior Design through Artificial Intelligence (AI)

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ABSTRACT

Recent years have seen the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) technology into our daily lives. Every industry sees revolutionary changes as a result of artificial intelligence (AI). Additionally, there are changes occurring in the fields of design and architecture. The conventional interior design industry has been somewhat altered by AI software. The revolutionary effects of AI on design practice and industry are examined in this study. From how people collaborate and generate ideas to the tools they use and the products they produce, this "digital transformation" is influencing nearly every facet of the design landscape. (Abdualee & Almnshdawy Hussain, 2024) AI innovation elevates interior design to new heights, merging art and technology seamlessly the researcher will be researching on "Transformation of Interior Design through AI". Using quantitative research methodology, the researcher hopes to understand how AI has affected Kolhapur city's interior design industry. 50 of the non-probability sampling method will use the snowball sampling method to choose the sample for this. Information will be gathered for that purpose via a google form questionnaire. For this, a close ended questions in questionnaire will be employed. In parallel, the researcher will gather information by gathering both primary and secondary data. The data gathered from it will undergo numerical analysis.

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence. interior design, revolution, digital transformation, innovation*

INTRODUCTION

The term Artificial Intelligence (AI) was stated by the scientist John McCarthy in 1956. He defined AI as: The science and engineering of making intelligent machines. (Lateef, 2023) Many scientists defined Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a study of how to make computers and system do things like human beings associated with intelligence. (Gupta & Mangla, 2020) Artificial Intelligence is considered as a branch of Computer science which can represent knowledge in terms of Text, Image, symbols nowadays that simulate the human intelligence, behaviour, understanding, Learning and problem solving...etc. The world has witnessed a boom in the development of Artificial Intelligence. The widespread availability of tools for artificial intelligence has the potential to radically alter the way people live, work & interact with their surroundings. The implication of AI technologies can be seen in all sectors today. In the design related industries human industries & human creativity & human touch are key aspects in new design driven development according to human needs. Design is undergoing a deep transformation driven by the rapid development of digital tools and technologies. This digital transformation affects almost every aspect of the design landscape, from how people think and work together to the tools they use and the products they create. What has changed in the Internet sector after the arrival of AI tool? Can AI tools or software replace or replace traditional software, and does the use of AI save time when working in the field of interior design? The researcher will study all these subjects in this research paper.[1,2]

Some AI powered tools used in Design industry like that AI Room planner, Homestyler, RoomGPT, Spacely AI, Getfloorplan, Coohom AI, Planner 5D, Interior AI, Midjourney, Leaperr,

DreamhouseAI, Reimagine Home, Canva AI, Figma AI, DecorMatters, RoomSketcher, Houzz pro, SmartDraw, HomevisualizerAI and many more. [25,26]

This research study delves into the landscape of Transformation of Interior Design through AI. This research study will provide guidelines for the way we consume AI powered tools in interior designing.[3]

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To find transformation in interior design through Artificial Intelligence (AI)
2. To find using artificial Intelligence tools in interior design

REVIEW OF LITERATURE**Digital transformation in design and the impact of modern tools and technologies**

In this article Mr. Almshawy Husain Abdulee, Mr.Karrar Hayder Mohammed says to analyses the evolutionary path of digital transformation and shows the influence of cultural transformation processes on it. In this essay, "digitalization" is defined as a change that increases the impact of the digital system on both its own operation and the sociocultural realm.[27,28]

Implementation of Artificial Intelligence in Interior Design: Systematic Literature Review

(Omar Adnan AIshiki, 2024) The results of a systematic literature review (SLR) are presented in this work with the goal of examining how artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly used into interior design, specifically to improve its efficiency, sustainability, and personalization. The findings indicate that AI has considerable potential to influence design process modifications & improve user experience through individual design choices & foster environmentally friendly design approaches.[22]

Application of Artificial Intelligence in Interior Design

(Zixuan Chen, 2020) Zixuan Chen Says this paper is about the combination of AI & home design, multi-angle analysis of the current development & prospects. Regarding the bedroom, kitchen, and children's items, storage problems provide solutions. Storage is an important problem for designers, and a difficult problem for users in their life. So, this paper is related to solving storage problems using AI tools.[33]

Artificial Intelligence (AI): Practices & Problems Experienced by Interior Designer

(Dr. Mona Mehta, 2024) Dr. Mona Mehta, Himani Shah, Rakhi Dasgupta says about this paper is the main aim of research study is to find out the practices & problems experience the interior designers regarding the applications of artificial intelligence in professionally managing & completing interior design projects.[11]

Article: Transforming Interior Design Education through Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) Trend

(Arisha, Transforming Interior Design Education through Generative Artificial Intelligence Trend, Dec 2023) In this research paper Nada Ahmed Arisha Says Interior designs generated from AI programs can be formed and applied in different design styles including traditional styles and new trends in contemporary design fields based on the database structured in AI Programs. In this paper she talks about types of Artificial Intelligence, components of artificial intelligence and many more. Researchers reviewed the related studies based on AI and Interior Designing which existed in the form of research papers and articles.[4,5]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study has been carried out in the geographical area of Kolhapur district. The present study employed by Quantitative research method. Target population for the research study is 50 samples architects and interior designers.[29,30]

The present study was based on primary as well as secondary sources of data. Researchers conducted surveys for collecting data using google form where planned and executed from 1st March 2025 to 19th March 2025. Secondary resources of the data were in existing form. Data from indirect sources such as literature reviews online databases is already collected for the present study in the form of secondary data.[6]

Researchers collected data using survey methods forming google form questionnaire. Researcher mentioned up to 10 questions in the google form based on about AI, importance of AI in interior design, AI powered tools in interior designing, challenges faced while using AI powered interior design tools, impact of AI in interior design sector, about benefits of AI in interior design, also researcher mentioned questions like that AI enhance creativity in interior designing and about AI make big difference in interior designing in future.[7,31]

For the present research study to know the personal information of the respondents as a sample researcher has taken indicators such as Name, Organization Name, Email Id and Mobile No. The data collected by the researcher using survey methods through Google form. Researcher herself collected the primary data. All the data analyzed by content analysis research design applying quantities analysis. The pie charts were created to analyse the data.[8]

About Respondents Knowing about the AI

In this question the focus is on the respondents having information about AI and they are known with it 50 respondents are collected 68% of respondents are known about AI, they answered Yes on the other hand 4% of respondents are unknown

about AI. Meanwhile, 28% of the respondents are few know about AI. Hence above given pie charts define the % of respondents is greater than the % of respondents who don't know about AI as compared to it.[9,32]

About Knowing AI Tools in Interior Designing

Researchers asked question about AI tools, and they are known for it 50 respondents are collected 56% of respondents are known about AI, they answered Yes on the other hand 44% of respondents are

unknown about AI. Hence above given pie charts qualify most of the respondents are known about Ai powered tools in interior designing.[10,33]

Responses About Use of AI Powered Tools in Interior Design

Researcher have taken responses about use of AI powered tools in interior design is only 42%

other hand 58% researcher don't use the Ai powered tools.[34]

About most used AI powered interior design tools.

The above given pie chart reflects the most used Ai powered interior design tools. According to the above given pie chart Ai Room planner is mostly preferred tool.26% respondents are using it.

Meanwhile RoomGPT is secondary used design tools. 12% of respondents are using it. Some of them are rarely used also there are some respondents who don't use AI powered tool anyway.[12,13]

Response about challenges faced by interior designers

This pie chart describes the challenges faced by interior designers while using AI tools. According to the given pie chart it comes to know that technical issues are the major challenge faced by designers and 44% of respondents are facing it. Meanwhile design quality is secondary

challenge faced by 28% of designers. On the other hand, cost is another challenge faced by 16% of respondents. There are very few no. of respondents who don't use any kind of AI tools and even they are away from it.[14,15]

Response about Opinion on AI Changing Interior Design Sector

The researcher focused on the opinion of the respondent about changing interior

design sector due to AI. Researchers found that 78% of respondents agreed that AI

changes interior design sector. On the other hand, 14% of respondents disagree about AI changing interior design sector. Also 8% of respondents don't know about it. It examines that there is large no. of

respondents who said yes, as compared to the respondents who said no and some of them who don't know about it. [16,17]

About having AI Tools Beneficial for Interior Designing

The researcher focusses on the question about having AI tools beneficial for interior designing regarding to the above given pie chart 76% of respondents have benefit of tool in manner to save time

while designing. 14% of them use for market survey and client interaction as well as estimation are rare benefits as per the pie chart. [18,19]

Response Upon Enhancement of Creativity in Interior Design

The present pie charts reflect the responses on enhancement of creativity in interior design as per the responses researcher came to that 52% of respondents enhance their creativity in design using tools. 30% of respondents are unsure about it.

Meanwhile 18% of respondents don't enhance any creativity in interior designing. The number of respondents who enhance creativity is greater than the respondents who are ensure about it. [20,21,35]

Response based on the Surety of AI Make Big Difference in Interior Design

As per pie charts given researchers analyzed the response on surety of AI make changes in interior designs in future. 64% of respondents agree to this question whereas 28% of respondents are unsure about it. 8% of respondents said no and it qualifies that they disagree with it. [23,24]

CONCLUSION

The present research study is concluded as follows,

- According to the first objective of the research, most of the interior designers and architects are not using AI Power tools. On the other hand 42% of Architects and Interior designers said AI powered tools are beneficial for interior designing in such a manner to save their time, market survey as well as client interactions and estimation. AI Power tools also enhance creativity in interior designs in various ways. Even though there are some challenges while operating AI power tools in interior designing. Hence the first objective of the research, to find transformation in interior design through artificial intelligence AI is proved.
- According to the second objective of the research there are various tools of interior design like AI room planner, Room GPT, Planner 5D, Home styler, Spicely Ai and so on. There is a large number of AI powered tool users in designing. Is the second objective, to find an artificial intelligence tool in interior design is proved.

REFERENCES

1. Abdualee, H., & Almnshdawy, H. (2024). Digital transformation in design and the impact of modern tools and technologies. *Global Prosperity*, 12, 1–12.
2. Almnshadwy, H. A., & Abdulee, K. H. (2024). Digital transformation in design and the impact of modern tools and technologies. *Global Prosperity*, 4(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10579329>
3. Almaz, A. F., El-Agouz, E. A., Abdel-Fateh, M. T., & Mohamed, I. R. (n.d.). The future role of artificial intelligence design integration into architectural and interior design education to improve efficiency, sustainability, and creativity. *Civil Engineering & Architecture*, 12(3), 1–12.
4. Arisha, N. A. (2023). Transforming interior design education through generative artificial intelligence (AI) trend. *Arts & Architecture Journal*, 5–6.
5. Arisha, N. A. (2023, December). Transforming interior design education through generative artificial intelligence trend. *Arts & Architecture Journal*, 18.
6. Adharsh, C., & A. (n.d.). AI-based interior design app. *Unpublished manuscript*, 1–4.
7. Hafiz, D. (2024, August 4). Shaping tomorrow: The impact of artificial intelligence on architectural history and interior design education. *ESIC 2024 Proceedings*, 8(2, Suppl. 2), 1–11.

8. Demirarslan, D. (2020, December 15). Digital technology and interior architecture. *Journal of Architecture & Life*, 15.
9. Aboushall, D. M. (2024, January). The effect of artificial intelligence on developing the interior designer's performance in interior architecture. *Unpublished research*, 1–16.
10. S. N. (n.d.). The future of interior design industry in the light of artificial intelligence spread. *Unpublished manuscript*, 1–18.
11. Mehta, M., & Singh, H. (2024, February 5). Artificial intelligence (AI): Practices and problems experienced by interior designers. *Shodhkosh: Journal of Visual & Performing Arts*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.29121/shodhkosh.v5.i2.2024.1424>
12. Lan, H., Tang, X., Fu, M., & Peng, H. (2025). Will human designers be replaced by AI involvement in interior design? *Current Psychology*, 7.
13. He, J. (2023, October 27). Research and implementation of intelligent interior design based on artificial intelligence and big data. *Conference paper*, Gwalior, India, 1–18.
14. Schneider, J., Sinem, K., & Stockhammer, D. (2023). Empowering clients: Transformation of design processes due to generative artificial intelligence. *Conference proceedings*, Liechtenstein.
15. Jansen, K. (n.d.). Artificial intelligence in interior design: A tool, not a threat—Why talented designers are irreplaceable. *Online article*, 1–4.
16. Li, M., & Lai, P. C. (2023). Interior design innovation ability with artificial intelligence and virtual reality technology. *DS Journal of Digital Science & Technology*, 10.
17. Kanchana, M. K. (2023, September). Impact of artificial intelligence-enabled tools on interior and exterior architectural designs. *Research article*, 1–10.
18. Musa, M. A. F. F. (2021). Digital architecture: Its impact on modeling of interior design of spaces. *Unpublished thesis*, 1–35.
19. Kahraman, M. U., Sekerci, Y., Develier, M., & Koyuncu, F. (2024, March 6). Integrating artificial intelligence in interior design education: Concept development. *Conference paper*, 1–30.
20. Monica, G. R., & Gowda, N. N. (2024). Impact of AI on commercial interior design: Enhancing functionality, aesthetics, and user experience. *Research article*, 1–5.
21. nmm. (2012). mmmm. oooo, 4.
22. Alshiki, O. A., & Z. B. (2024). Implementation of artificial intelligence in interior design: A systematic literature review. *Review article*, 1–18.
23. P., O. P. (2024). Transformation of methods of art object use in interior design. *Culture & Arts in the Modern World*, 17.
24. Patil, R. A., Wankhede, V., & Patil, B. (n.d.). A comparative study of generative AI models for interior design. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology*, 8.
25. Karrar, S. Y. W. A. (2023). The impact of artificial intelligence applications in interior design and monitoring of pros and cons through applied experiments. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies in Art & Technology*, 24.
26. Mahendarto, T. (2025, February). History of artificial intelligence and its potential to revolutionize the interior design industry. *JARINA: Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Architecture*, 13.
27. Lesmana, V. A. A., Cahyadi, A. T. E., & Tanti, S. R. (2024, May 13). Optimising artificial intelligence's role in advancing the interior design

- industry. *JARINA: Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Architecture*, 10.
28. Yang, X. (2024). The application of intelligent technology in interior design and its impact on living experience. *Research article*, 4.
29. Li, Y. (2024). Research on the publication of artificial intelligence in interior design. *International Journal of Science & Engineering Applications*, 6.
30. Sekeri, Y., Develier, M., & Kahraman, M. U. (2014, May). Artificial intelligence integration in interior design studio: Students' perspective. *Conference paper*, 17.
31. Shao, Z., & C. J. (2024). A new approach to interior design: Generating creative interior design videos of various styles from indoor texture-free 3D models. *Buildings*, 202, 1–10.
32. Zhao, Z. (2024, January 9). A study on the application of artificial intelligence in modern interior design and its impact on design efficiency. *Research article*, 1–25.
33. Chen, Z., & Wang, X. (2020). Application of artificial intelligence in interior design. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 179, 02105. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202017902105>
34. Marymount University. (n.d.). How AI is revolutionizing interior design and how to successfully use AI as an interior designer. *Marymount University Blog*. <https://marymount.edu/blog/how-ai-is-revolutionizing-interior-design-and-how-to-successfully-use-ai-as-an-interior-designer/>
35. Portugal, C. (2024). 5 ways to use AI to improve your survey research. *Insight Platforms*. <https://www.insightplatforms.com/5-ways-to-use-ai-to-improve-your-survey-research/>